

The Effect of Human Resources Management Practices on the Firm's Productivity and Profitability

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Abstract: *The concept of Human Resources Management has increased in the strategies of companies. Indeed, now companies are searching for new practices to improve its performance, productivity and the position of competitiveness. Moreover, Human Resources Management is an important tool for organizational competitiveness. This paper examined the impact of the key practice of human resources management, i.e., Communication on the firm's Productivity and Profitability. This research is conducted in Karachi Textile Industry, and respondents are selected by random sampling technique and responses were collected with the help of close ended questionnaires. Communication is taken as an independent variable and firm's Productivity, and Profitability took as dependent variables. Quantitative and Qualitative research approaches are used to examine the impact of HRM Practices on the dependent variables. Two hypothesis was constructed. To test the hypothesis, a regression analysis was used. The results showed that both hypotheses were accepted. Communication has a significant impact on both, firm's productivity and profitability. In this study, SPSS 18 was used. This study also helps us to understand the significance of Communication and its impact on the mention of dependent variables. The result of this study can be useful for business practitioners and as well as academics who are interested in the Karachi textile Milan ls*

Keywords: *Human Resources Management, Communication, Productivity, Profitability*

Introduction:

Human resources management is the very broad concept in the field of management. It has a very profound impact on the performance of employees as well as firms. So we should give the very much importance to this concept. The task of Human resources management starts with interview, placement, orientation, and end on retirement or firing of employees. This department plays a vital role for both employees and firms. As we mention above that the task of human resources management has very broadened and now it is not traditionally or specific. its activities are much more important than other. Unfortunately, the concept of human resources management is not understood in the developing countries as it should be, even its concept is not applied according to international standard. HR task is not only related with the particular or specific process of recruitment, selection, training, and development, etc. but also its scope has become very broad to many new and distinguished areas (Jamil & al, 2011). There is a positive relationship between Human Resources practices and firm performance (Ahmad & Shahzad, 2011). The HR practice has a great effect on the firm's performance, but unfortunately in developing countries, there is not sufficient research are done in this areas (Mohammad & Absar, 2010). HRM practice enhances the organizational performance also a potential and power source of sustainable competitive advantage for an organization and shows the positive relationship between firm performance (Gooderham & at, 2008) .

The most important and influential task of human resources management is "Communication." it is taken as a key role in any organization. it may be internal and external, verbal and non-verbal, downward and upward. In downward communication orders and instruction are given by superiors and in upward communication request and commitment is done by employees. Communication is the very important tool in any organization to improve the performance of employees as well as firms (Gooderham & at, 2008). The manager cannot achieve the organizational goal if he is not able to communicate effectively. There are different variables which have been discussed in the previous researches, but in this paper, we are going to discuss the very important aspects of human resources management which is "Communication." we want to examine the impact of communication on the productivity and firm's profitability

Literature Review:

Communication: Communication as the action of exchanging information or ideas (oxford dictionary). Communication is the flow of news, ideas, information or the process of two-way to reached mutual

understanding, in which a person not only exchange ideas, news, feelings, and information but also it create and share meaning. Effective communication is very effective in all areas of business whether it is verbal or nonverbal. The importance of communication cannot be denied in any business organization. The following are the main features of effective business communication.

Lifeblood: the organization cannot function without the effective communication system, where the group of peoples associated with other activities. Which require a human being to relate each other to work as a team which increases the productivity and profitability (Ahmad & Shahzad, 2011).

Communication In organization: the more effective communication system, the more its help to increase the productivity and Profitability (A.Huselid, 1995)

Advantages for personal careers: the ability of one`s communication can put it a step forward over other. The person who has this ability has great advantages (Green, 2012).

Communication plays a vital role in every department of the organization, but for human resources, department communication is the lifeblood. Because the task of this department starts from selection, interview, orientation, training, motivation till retirement or firing. It has the direct relation with the turnover, productivity and firm`s Profitability so communication in HR department is very important rather than any other department because the human resources manager`s interaction within the organization and outside the organization is very important. Nowadays In human resources management field, the impact of HRM practices on the firm's performance has become a very important topic which has a profound effect on the productivity, turnover, profitability of the firm (A.Huselid, 1995). According to (Udegbe & at, 2012) the companies which are practicing effective business communication, reduce the employees turnover, increase productivity and improved firms profitability. According to (Green, 2012) without good communication skills, a manager cannot implement the management process, and the organizational goal cannot be achieved. So communication improves the efficiency of both firms and employees. According to (Wanjikukibe, 2014) Communication is a symptom of the organization and the cause of any organization performance problems. Communication is the factors in human resources management which is responsible for mobilizing and directing the labor force toward the completeness of organizational objectives and goals (Chidiebere.S, Precious Ngozi, & OKONKWO, 2015).

Conceptual Framework

Conceptual Framework

Firms Productivity and Profitability:

In the age of globalization, business has become more challenging to stay profitable but, in all factors of human production resources is very challenging to manage because of feelings and emotions factors (Shonubi & Akintaro, 2015). The effectively managing human resources activities result in low employee turnover (Syed,

Farooq, & at, 2013). The implementing HRM practices have been experienced to lower turnover rates for non-managerial employees (Seonghee, Robert, & at, 2006). HR professionals to argue that Human Resources practices lead to greater employee satisfaction and a reduction in employee turnover that improve a firm's performance (Choi, 2009). Happy employees are always productive employees so good HR practice cause of high satisfaction with the job, high productivity, decrease the turnover rate and low absenteeism in the workplace (NurunNabi & at, 2016). HRM practice closely associates with low labor turnover and higher profit per employee (Guest & at, 2003).

Research Questions:

This study was done to explore the answer to the following research questions (RQ):

RQ1: Is there any association between communication and Productivity.?

RQ2: Is there any association between communication and the Firm's Profitability.?

Hypothesis:

H1: Communication has a positive impact on productivity.

H2: Communication has a positive impact on a firm's profitability.

Research Methodology:

Regression analysis emphasizes on the casual relationship between Y and X. the basic objective of regression analysis is to explain the on average behavior of Y in relation to the regressors, i.e., X. it clarifies how to mean Y responds to the changes in the values of X variable (Gujarati). In this study, regression analysis is applied in order to check the impact of communication on the firm's productivity and profitability. The Population consists of Textile Industry of Pakistan. In the context of the Karachi. The Random simple technique is used in this research and responses were collected with the help of close ended questionnaires. The impact of communication was shown on firm's productivity and profitability; all variables were measured on the five points Likert scale which tell us that how the respondent strongly agrees or disagrees with the statement stated in the questionnaire. For data analysis, SPSS 18 was used.

Empirical Model:

$$Y = C + Bx_1 + E_t$$

Y = firm's productivity and profitability

C = intercept or constant

B = slope

X₁ = Communication

E_t = error term

Data Collection:

Primary data were collected through the close ended questionnaires from the Senior , Middle and Junior Managers, working in textile industries in Karachi.

Key: 5: Strongly Agree

4: Agree

3: Neutral

2: Disagree

1: Strongly Disagree

S.NO	Questions	1	2	3	4	5	Total
1-	Non-verbal communication is effective for the organization performance.	61.54%	30.77%	-	7.69%	-	100%
2-	Present communication channel (such as written and oral) is very effective for organization.	-	-	-	92.31%	7.69%	100%
3-	The degree of Coordination among various departments (such as Account, Marketing and Production) is very high.	-	-	-	23.08%	76.92%	100%
4-	Written Communication is time consuming channel	-	-	-	100%	-	100%
5-	There are opportunities to lower staff to express their ideas regarding firm performance	-	-	23.06%	76.94%	-	100%
6-	Language is a barrier in effective communication system within organization	-	-	-	30.77%	69.23%	100%
7-	Lower staff clearly knows their task	7.69%	46.15%	15.38%	30.77%	-	100%
8-	Communication skills of upper management is very effective	-	-	-	100%	-	100%
9-	Good communication improved the firm's productivity	-	-	-	100%	-	100%
10-	Good relationship between managers and lower staff increasing the firm's productivity	-	-	-	84.62%	15.38%	100%
11-	Manager and Executive taking interest in employee's activities	38.46%	15.38%	23.08%	23.08%	-	100%
12-	In your organization, two way communication between managers and employees is very effective.	-	-	7.69%	92.31%	-	100%
13-	A good communication system has a positive impact on the profitability of the firm.	-	-	-	7.69%	92.31%	100%

Demographic Variables:

	Percentage
Age	
20-29	8%
30-39	30%
40+	62%
Total	
Education	
Inter	8%
Bachelor	15%
Master-Above	77%
Total	
Department	
Procurement/Production	61%
HR	8%
Admin	8%
Finance	8%
Quality Assurance	15%
Total	
Designation	
Ass. Manager Planning & Production	38%
Quality Manager	8%
Ass. Manager Finance	8%
Purchase/Merchandiser	22%
HR Manager	8%
Admin Manager	8%
Supply Chain Manager	8%
Total	
Duration of Service	
3 to 5 years	38%
6 to 8 years	38%
9 to 11 years	15%
12+ years	9%
Total	

Result Analysis:

The following result has been extracted from the above close ended questionnaires.

Age Of The Respondents

	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 20-29	7.7	7.7	7.7
30-39	38.5	38.5	46.2
40 and above	53.8	53.8	100.0
Total	100.0	100.0	

Education Of The Respondents

	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Intermediate	15.4	15.4	15.4
Bachelor	23.1	23.1	38.5
Masters and Above	61.5	61.5	100.0
Total	100.0	100.0	

Department Of The Respondents

	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Production	69.2	69.2	69.2
HR	7.7	7.7	76.9
Finance	7.7	7.7	84.6
Quality Assurance	15.4	15.4	100.0
Total	100.0	100.0	

Designation Of The Respondents

	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Assistant Manager Planning and Production	61.5	61.5	61.5
Quality Manager	15.4	15.4	76.9
Assistant Manager Finance	7.7	7.7	84.6
Purchase	7.7	7.7	92.3
Admin	7.7	7.7	100.0
Total	100.0	100.0	

Duration Of The Respondents

	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 6-8 Years	53.8	53.8	53.8
9-11 Years	23.1	23.1	76.9
12 Years and Above	23.1	23.1	100.0
Total	100.0	100.0	

Non-Verbal communication is effective for the organization performance

	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	61.5	61.5	61.5
Disagree	30.8	30.8	92.3
Agree	7.7	7.7	100.0
Total	100.0	100.0	

Present communication channel (such as written and oral) is very effective for organization

	Perce nt	Valid Percent	Cumulativ e Percent
Vali d Agree	92.3	92.3	92.3
Strongly Agree	7.7	7.7	100.0
Total	100.0	100.0	

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The degree of Coordination among various departments (such as Account, Marketing and Production) is very high.

	Perce nt	Valid Percent	Cumulati ve Percent
Vali d Agree	23.1	23.1	23.1
Strongly Agree	76.9	76.9	100.0
Total	100.0	100.0	

The degree of Coordination among various departments (such as Account, Marketing and Production) is very high.

Written Communication is time consuming channel

	Perce nt	Valid Percent	Cumulativ e Percent
Vali d Agree	100.0	100.0	100.0

Written Communication is time consuming channel

There are opportunities to lower staff to express their ideas regarding firm performance

		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral	23.1	23.1	23.1
	Agree	76.9	76.9	100.0
	Total	100.0	100.0	

There are opportunities to lower staff to express their ideas regarding firm performance

Language is a barrier in effective communication system within organization

		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	30.8	30.8	30.8
	Strongly Agree	69.2	69.2	100.0
	Total	100.0	100.0	

Language is a barrier in effective communication system within organization

Lower staff clearly knows their task

		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7.7	7.7	7.7
	Disagree	46.2	46.2	53.8
	Neutral	15.4	15.4	69.2
	Agree	30.8	30.8	100.0
	Total	100.0	100.0	

Lower staff clearly knows their task

Communication skills of upper management is very effective

	Perce nt	Valid Percent	Cumulati ve Percent
Vali Agr d ee	100.0	100.0	100.0

Good communication improved the firm's productivity

	Perce nt	Valid Percent	Cumulati ve Percent
Vali Agr d ee	100.0	100.0	100.0

Good relationship between managers and lower staff increasing the firm's productivity

	Perce nt	Valid Percent	Cumulativ e Percent
Vali Agree	84.6	84.6	84.6
d Strongly Agree	15.4	15.4	100.0
Total	100.0	100.0	

Manager and Executive taking interest in employee's activities

	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	38.5	38.5	38.5
Disagree	15.4	15.4	53.8
Neutral	23.1	23.1	76.9
Agree	23.1	23.1	100.0
Total	100.0	100.0	

In your organization two way communications between managers and employees is very effective.

	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Neutral	7.7	7.7	7.7
Agree	92.3	92.3	100.0
Total	100.0	100.0	

A good communication system has a positive impact on the profitability of firm

	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Agree	7.7	7.7	7.7
Strongly Agree	92.3	92.3	100.0
Total	100.0	100.0	

Results Analysis:

The result of linear regression analysis indicate in table no.1 that R square is 0.967 which shows that total variation in firm`s productivity and profitability brought by the communication is about 93.6% which is quite satisfactory.

Table No.1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.967	.936	.807	.12197	.936	7.256	8	4	.036	2.279

Moreover, the confidence interval in this study is set for 95%. So the value of alpha was 0.05. the overall significance of the statistical model shown in table no.2 as F-Statistics = 7.256>1 indicates that the model was significant and is explaining the total variation in the dependent variable is satisfactory.

Table No.2: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.864	8	.108	7.256	.036
	Residual	.060	4	.015		
	Total	.923	12			

As in Table No.3, Beta Values indicate results that if for every 1 unit increase so how many it will have an effect on customer purchase intention.

Q1	0.951
Q2	-0.200
Q3	-0.447
Q4	0.461
Q5	-1.211
Q6	0.468
Q7	-0.127
Q8	0.036

Thus as result indicate that non-verbal communication is effective for organization performance because it has a greater effect on the firm`s productivity and profitability it is showing 0.951 which is highest, secondly Good relationship between managers and lower staff has a positive impact on the film's productivity and profitability because it is showing 0.468, the third Language is a barrier ineffective communication system within an organization which is showing 0.461. on the other hand, the other mentioned independent variables have a very low or negative impact on the firm`s productivity and profitability.

Table No.3: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.739	2.455		1.930	.126
	Q1: Non-Verbal communication is effective for the organization performance	.301	.323	.951	.930	.405
	Q2: Present communication channel is very effective for organization	-.200	.919	-.200	-.218	.838
	Q3: The degree of Coordination among various departments (such as Account, Marketing, and Production) is very high.	-.283	.343	-.447	-.824	.456
	Q4: Language is a barrier in effective communication system within organization	.266	.119	.461	2.240	.089
	Q5: Lower staff clearly knows their task	-.326	.073	-1.211	-4.468	.011
	Q6: Good relationship between managers and lower staff increasing the firm's productivity	.345	.204	.468	1.693	.166
	Q7: Manager and Executive taking interest in employee's activities	-.028	.043	-.127	-.650	.551
	Q8: In your organization, two way communication between managers and employees is very effective.	.036	.218	.036	.167	.876

a. Dependent Variable: A good communication system has a positive impact on the profitability of the firm

Conclusion:

This research was aimed to observe that whether Communication in the organization can create a positive impact on a firm's productivity and profitability. For this purpose, one independent variable (i.e., Communication) was selected, and the dependent variables were the firm's productivity and profitability. Based on these variables, two hypothesis was constructed. H₁: Communication has a positive impact on productivity and H₂: Communication has a positive impact on a firm's profitability. Data was collected through questionnaires from the different areas of Karachi. To test the hypothesis, regression analysis was applied. SPSS 18 was used. The results show that both hypotheses were accepted and the result showed that Communication has significant impact on both, firm's productivity and profitability.

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